

Bromination of Steroidal-6-ketoximes

SHAFIULLAH*, JAVED A. ANSARI and SHAHID A. ANSARI

Steroid Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 002

Manuscript received 18 January 1988, accepted 19 February 1988

Bromination of 5 α -cholestan-6-one oxime (1) with *N*-bromosuccinimide in carbon tetrachloride using benzoyl peroxide as a catalyst gave 6 β -nitro-7 α -bromocholest-4-ene (4), 7-bromocholesta-4,7-dien-6-one (5), 5 α -cholestan-6-one (6) and 6-nitrocholest-5-ene (7). 3 β -Chloro-5 α -cholestan-6-one oxime (2) on similar treatment afforded 3 β -chloro-5-bromo-5 α -cholestan-6-one (8), 3 β -chloro-5 α ,7-dibromocholest-7-en-6-one (9) and 3 β -chloro-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (10). Under similar reaction conditions, 3 β -acetoxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one oxime (3) yielded 3 β -acetoxy-5,7 β -dibromo-5 α -cholestan-6-one (11), 3 β -acetoxy-7-bromocholesta-4,7-dien-6-one (12), 3 β -acetoxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (13) and 3 β -acetoxy-5 α ,7-dibromo-6 β -nitrocholest-7-ene (14). The identity of the products has been established on the basis of their spectral data and comparison with authentic samples in known cases.

PREVIOUS work from these laboratories described the allylic bromination of steroidal nitroolefins¹ and bromination of α,β -unsaturated ketones² using *N*-bromosuccinimide and bromine in acetic acid, respectively. This paper is concerned with the bromination of the easily accessible steroidal-6-ketoximes (1-3).

Compound 1³ on treatment with *N*-bromosuccinimide using benzoyl peroxide as a catalyst in carbon tetrachloride afforded 4-7. The elemental analysis of 4 showed its composition as C₂₇H₄₄O₂NBr; gave positive Beilstein test; $\nu_{\max}$ 1550, 1470 and 1375 (non-conjugated NO₂)⁴ and 665 cm⁻¹ (CBr)⁵, which showed that bromine at C7 is axial (α) oriented. ¹H nmr spectra displayed a broad singlet at δ 5.40 (C7- β H, *W*_{1/2} 3 Hz, equatorial) which suggests the presence of bromine at C7 position as axial. A broad singlet for one proton at δ 5.66 (C4-vinyl proton) and a distorted doublet at δ 4.55 (C6- α H) were also found. The compound 5 was analysed for C₂₇H₄₁OBr; gave positive Beilstein test for halogen; $\nu_{\max}$ 1700 (C=O), 1650 (C=C) and 750 cm⁻¹ (CBr)⁶. ¹H nmr spectra

gave a broad singlet at δ 5.33 ascribable for C4-vinyl proton. Compounds 6⁷ and 7⁸ were found identical (m.p., m.m.p., tlc and ir) with the authentic samples of 5 α -cholestan-6-one and 6-nitrocholest-5-ene, respectively.

The ketoxime (2)⁹ on similar treatment gave 8-10. 8¹⁰ and 10¹¹ were found identical (m.p., m.m.p., tlc, ir and nmr) with authentic samples of 3 β -chloro-5-bromo-5 α -cholestan-6-one and 3 β -chloro-6-nitrocholest-5-ene, respectively. 9 had correct analysis as C₂₇H₄₁ClBr₂; gave positive Beilstein test; $\nu_{\max}$ 1705 (C=O), 1630 (C=C), 760 (CCl) and 670 cm⁻¹ (CBr). ¹H nmr spectra of 9 exhibited a broad multiplet at δ 4.51 (C3- α H, *W*_{1/2} 16 Hz, axial).

Under similar reaction conditions, 3¹² yielded 11-14. Compounds 11¹³ and 13¹⁴ were found identical (m.p., m.m.p., tlc, ir and nmr) with authentic samples of 3 β -acetoxy-5,7 β -dibromo-5 α -cholestan-6-one and 3 β -acetoxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene, respectively. The elemental analysis of 12 showed its composition as C₂₉H₄₈O₃Br; gave positive Beilstein test; $\nu_{\max}$ 1735 and 1700 (acetate and unsaturated carbonyl), 1240 and 1045 (C-O) and 750 cm⁻¹ (CBr). ¹H nmr spectra of 12 showed a broad singlet at δ 5.7 (C4-vinyl proton), a broad multiplet at δ 4.45 (C3- α H, *W*_{1/2} 18 Hz, axial), a singlet at δ 2.1 (CH₃COO). The elemental analysis of 14 showed its composition as C₂₉H₄₅O₄NBr₂; gave positive Beilstein test for halogen; $\nu_{\max}$ 1735 (CH₃COO), 1630 (C=C), 1565, 1470 and 1375 (non-conjugated NO₂), 1245 and 1035 (C-O) and 745 cm⁻¹ (CBr). ¹H nmr spectra of 14 exhibited a multiplet for two protons at δ 4.6 (C3- α H and C6- α H) and a singlet at δ 1.95 for (CH₃COO).

Experimental

All m.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were determined with a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectro-

photometer and ^1H nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Varian A-60 instrument with Me_4Si as the internal standard. Tlc plates were coated with silica gel and an aqueous 20% perchloric acid solution was used as the spraying agent. Anhydrous sodium sulphate was used as a drying agent. Light petroleum ether refers to fraction having b.p. 60–80°. The angular and side chain methyl protons appeared in nmr spectra between δ 0.68–1.29.

General procedure: To a solution of **1** (3.0 g) in carbon tetrachloride (400 ml), *N*-bromosuccinimide (3.0 g) was added with a few crystals of benzoyl peroxide as catalyst. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h on a water-bath and the progress of the reaction was monitored by tlc. After cooling, the resulting insoluble succinimide was filtered off and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. A dark brown residue thus obtained was chromatographed over silica gel (60 g). Elution with light petroleum ether gave 6 β -nitro-7 α -bromocholest-4-ene (**4**; 200 mg, oil) (Found: C, 65.49; H, 8.85; N, 2.80. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{44}\text{O}_2\text{NBr}$ requires: C, 65.62; H, 8.90; N, 2.83%). Further elution with light petroleum ether–ether (30 : 1) afforded 7-bromocholesta-4,7-dien-6-one (**5**; 150 mg, oil) (Found: C, 70.28; H, 8.86. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{41}\text{OBr}$ requires: C, 70.31, H, 8.89%). Further elution with light petroleum ether–ether (22 : 1) gave 5 α -cholestan-6-one (**6**; 800 mg), which was crystallised from methanol, m.p. and m.m.p. 97° (lit.⁷ 98°). Finally, elution with light petroleum ether–ether (18 : 1) yielded 6-nitrocholest-5-ene (**7**; 600 mg) which was crystallised from methanol, m.p. and m.m.p. 119° (lit.⁸ 119–20°).

Under similar reaction conditions, **2** provided **8–10**. The same amounts of the reactants were used and the oily residue obtained was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with light petroleum ether–ether (20 : 1) gave 3 β -chloro-5 α -cholestan-6-one (**8**; 500 mg) which was crystallised from methanol, m.p. and m.m.p. 123° (lit.⁹ 124°). Further elution with light petroleum ether–ether (18 : 1) afforded 3 β -chloro-5 α ,7-dibromocholest-7-en-6-one (**9**; 450 mg, oil) (Found: C, 56.20; H, 70.12. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{41}\text{OBr}_2\text{Cl}$ requires: C, 56.24, H, 70.11%). Further elution with light petroleum ether–ether (10 : 1) gave 3 β -chloro-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (**10**; 750 mg) which was crystallised from methanol, m.p. and m.m.p. 151.5° (lit.¹¹ 152°).

The reaction of **3** under similar conditions gave an oily residue which was chromatographed over

silica gel. Elution with light petroleum ether–ether (30 : 1) gave 3 β -acetoxy-5,7 β -dibromo-5 α -cholestan-6-one (**11**; 450 mg), which was crystallised from methanol, m.p. and m.m.p. 138° (lit.¹² 140°). Further elution with light petroleum ether–ether (25 : 1) afforded 3 β -acetoxy-7-bromocholesta-4,7-dien-6-one (**12**; 670 mg), which was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 137° (Found: C, 67.06; H, 8.26. $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_3\text{Br}$ requires: C, 67.08; H, 8.28%). Further elution with light petroleum ether–ether (20 : 1) yielded 3 β -acetoxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (**13**; 550 mg), which was crystallised from methanol, m.p. and m.m.p. 103° (lit.¹⁴ 102–04°). Finally, elution with light petroleum ether–ether (18 : 1) afforded 3 β -acetoxy-5 α ,7 β -dibromo-6 β -nitrocholest-7-ene (**14**; 750 mg), which was crystallised from acetone, m.p. 142° (Found: C, 55.17; H, 7.11; N, 2.19. $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_4\text{NBr}_2$ requires: C, 55.19; H, 7.13; N, 2.21%).

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. M. S. Ahmad, and Prof. S. M. Osman, Chairman, Department of Chemistry, for facilities and encouragement.

References

- SHAFIULLAH, S. HUSAIN, H. ALI, H. OGURA and H. TAKAYANAGI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1983, **22**, 71.
- SHAFIULLAH, E. A. KHAN, H. OGURA and H. TAKAYANAGI, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1979, 2727.
- O. W. SHOPPÉE, R. E. LACK and S. K. ROY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 3767.
- J. T. PINNEY and C. G. SMITH, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1978, **31**, 2563.
- D. H. R. BARTON, J. E. PAGE and C. W. SHOPPÉE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 331.
- L. J. BELLAMY, "Infrared Spectra of Complex Organic Molecules", Wiley, New York, 1958, p. 332.
- C. W. SHOPPÉE, D. N. JONES, J. R. LEWIS and G. H. B. SUMMERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 2876.
- J. R. BULL, E. R. H. JONES and G. D. MEAKINS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 2601.
- E. G. FORD, P. CHAKRAVORTY and E. S. WALLIS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 418.
- SHAFIULLAH and ISLAMUDDIN, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1980, **53**, 523.
- N. F. BLAU and C. G. STUCKWISCH, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, **27**, 370.
- L. KNOF, *Justus Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1962, **642**, 194.
- M. S. AHMAD, N. Z. KHAN and Z. FAROOQ, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **12**, 452.
- C. E. ANAGNOSTOPOULOS and L. F. FISHER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 532.